

Towards standardization of electrogastrography

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Letter to Editor:² Current status of measurement instrumentation and data analysis in EGG (ElectroGastroGraphy), including novel decision algorithm for estimation of EGG signal reliability and results of signal analysis performed on EGG signals recorded in 117 healthy volunteers were recently presented in [1]. We strongly agree with the statement made by the authors in [1] that the main limitation of EGG methodology is the lack of standardization. Although, we believe that authors in [1] provided substantial scientific contribution to the EGG field, we address important recording setup elements that were overlooked.

Authors in [1] did not report the gain of EGG amplifiers. Also, it is not stated whether active electrodes were used with BioSemi system as suggested on manufacturer's website [2]. Usage of additional amplification step by application of active electrodes could make significant change in the signal properties and its characteristics (gain and frequency content). Also, its application could possibly lead to higher signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in comparison to EGG signals recorded by application of high pass filter and instrumentation amplifier as we proposed earlier in [3]. We believe that active electrode application (i.e., pre-amplification stage) should be reported together with the gain in order to enable replication of the recording procedure and adequate comparisons where applicable.

On DC abbreviation³: it is used for both Direct Current and for Direct-coupled, the latter being commonly used for "DC amplifier" [4]. After application of DC (Direct-coupled) amplifier as in [1] the resulting EGG signal has entire spectrum with AC (Alternating Current) and DC (Direct Current) components⁴. On the other hand, obsolete existing terminology in power engineering uses DC (Direct Current) amplifier for amplifier that aims to produce solely DC (Direct Current) component [5]. Also, in electrical measurements, for oscilloscope user interface, DC abbreviation (Direct Current) is used with the word coupling for "DC coupling" that shows entire signal and AC (Alternating Current) is used in "AC coupling" that presents signal when DC (Direct Current) component is filtered

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³ For the sake of clarity, we explained AC and DC abbreviations on all mentions.

⁴ It is not known whether in [1] active electrodes were used and whether they had also high pass filter part.

out (signal is centered around 0 V) [6]. For multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary research, it is important to explain all abbreviations without exception in order to avoid misinterpretation.

To conclude – a complete specification of the measurement instrumentation with explanations of all abbreviations, regardless how common they are in one field, are necessary in order to avoid potentially problematic practices and misrepresentation and to enable replicability [7]. Future standardization and concerned actions are required for exchange of knowledge and experiences in the area of EGG, similar to other initiatives in electrophysiology such as SENIAM (Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles) recommendations for surface electromyography [8].

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References

1. Wolpert N, Rebollo I, Tallon-Baudry C. Electrogastrography for psychophysiological research: Practical considerations, analysis pipeline, and normative data in a large sample. *Psychophysiology* 2020; **e13599**. doi: [10.1111/psyp.13599](https://doi.org/10.1111/psyp.13599)
2. BioSemi products for research applications, Amsterdam, Netherlands. [Online] <https://www.biosemi.com/>, Assessed on August 6, 2020.
3. Popović NB, Miljković N, Stojmenova K, Jakus G, Prodanov M, Sodnik J. Lessons learned: Gastric motility assessment during driving simulation. *Sensors* 2019; **19**(14):3175. doi: [10.3390/s19143175](https://doi.org/10.3390/s19143175)
4. Fabre A, Seguin F, Zouaoui Abouda H, Barthelemy H. DC Amplifiers. In *Wiley Encyclopedia of Electrical and Electronics Engineering* 1999; J.G. Webster (Ed.). doi: [10.1002/047134608X.W2227](https://doi.org/10.1002/047134608X.W2227)
5. Gall DC. A direct-current amplifier and its application to industrial measurements and control. *Journal of the Institution of Electrical Engineers-Part II: Power Engineering* 1942; **89**(11), 434-443. doi: [10.1049/ji-2.1942.0072](https://doi.org/10.1049/ji-2.1942.0072)
6. XYZs of Oscilloscopes, Primer, Chapter 4: Oscilloscope Systems and Controls Tektronix, 2016; 1-60. [Online] https://download.tek.com/document/03W_8605_7_HR_Letter.pdf, Assessed on July 29, 2020.
7. Open Science Collaboration. Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science* 2015; **349**:6251. doi: [10.1126/science.aac4716](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac4716)
8. Hermens HJ, Freriks B, Disselhorst-Klug C, Rau G. Development of recommendations for SEMG sensors and sensor placement procedures. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology* 2000; **10**(5):361-374. doi: [10.1016/S1050-6411\(00\)00027-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1050-6411(00)00027-4)